

A Study of Variation in Agricultural Labourers in Latur District

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Abstract:

Agriculture is the backbone of the Indian economy. It is the prime sector of the Indian economy. At the initial stage of development Indian economy was an agrarian economy and it was depend on agricultural labourers. Thus, agricultural labourers have been playing a crucial role in the economy for last 70 years after independence. In this paper, the researcher has attempted to explain proportional changes in agricultural labourers in Latur district. Using census reports of Latur district between 1991 and 2011, the variation in agricultural labourers has been explained.

Keywords: *Agricultural Labourers, Agriculture, Latur district.*

Introduction:

Agriculture is the backbone of the Indian economy. It is a primary source of livelihood for 70 percent of Indians. "Traditionally, agriculture is the prime sector of rural economy and employment." (Ramesh Chand, November 2017) In India, most agricultural labourers belong to the scheduled caste, Scheduled Tribal, and Other Backward Communities. It is the poorest section of Indian society. Since they belong to a Scheduled caste and scheduled tribe they have low social status in Indian society. They have been ignored for centuries by the Indian society and planners. They receive low wage that lead to low income therefore they face poverty problems. This paper examines the variation in the number of agricultural laborers and the number of male and female agricultural

labourers in Latur district from 1991 to 2001 and 2001 to 2011.

Objective of the Study:

1. To find out the variation in agricultural labourers in Latur district.
2. To find out the variation in male agricultural labourers in Latur district.
3. To find out the variation in female agricultural labourers in Latur district.

Limitation of the Study:

The present study is only applicable only for the geographical area of the Latur district of the Marathwada region of Maharashtra state.

Research Methodology:

The present study is based on the secondary data collected through the different years of census reports of Latur

district published by the government of Maharashtra.

Review of Literature:

The researcher has taken review of various research papers and report to conduct the present study.

Anbarasan. P. (May, 2019) in his study, To determine wage growth rates under MGNREGA, secondary data was collected from various journals and e-resources. India is the world's second largest producer of meat and milk after the United States, as well as the biggest producer of rice, wheat, vegetables, fruits, and sugarcane. He stated that, approximately 90 percent of the labor force works in agriculture and small businesses. The agriculture sector employs about half of the labor force. The percentage of agricultural workers in the total workforce declined from 72.36 percent in 1961 to 52.61 percent in 2011, respectively. The percentage of cultivators to the total work force has also declined from 51.8% in 1961 to 22.60 in 2011. In 2011, the share of agricultural workers rose from 19.56% to 30%. The compound annual growth rate of MGNREGA wages during the period 2006-07 to 2016-17 was 12 percent. The wage rates were 69 rupees in 2006-07 and 224 rupees in 2016-17. Despite the fact that the agricultural labor force has increased since 1961, rural labourers now have certainty of employment thanks to MGNREGA, which encourages them to work in agriculture.

B. V. Raju (Nov, 2017) According to the researcher, Krishna district in Andhra Pradesh is the study area. According to the government report, 44% of the population in this district is employed as agriculture labourers, and they belong to the Schedule castes and Schedule tribes. They belong to suppressed class. In addition, he explained that agriculture labourers earn irregular wages. The majority of labourers are in poverty because they lack alternative employment opportunities to earn income. As a result of poor implementation, they were unable to get enough wage, resulting in poverty cycle among them, even though their wage rate was revised upward. Their economic status is therefore very low. Because legislation regarding them has not been enforced permanently, they don't have social security.

Chand Ramesh, Srivatava S. K. and Singh Jaspal (2017) He has discussed about the defeminisation in agriculture. Households of agricultural laborers, which are poor economically. The majorities of women stay home and avoid farm work, and female agricultural labor households do not prefer to work on farms. It is possible that the defeminization of rural workforce has been driven more by the lack of non-farm employment opportunities than by a lack of willingness to work outside the home. There should be more attractive avenues for women to engage in productive work after 2011-12, as women's participation in the labour force declined.

Das Gobind Kumar (July 2020) in his study, he has discussed about the employment of agricultural labour in India. The study is based on the secondary data. According to him, agriculture provides employment to 1.3 billion people. Half of the global workforce is employed by agriculture, with most of these workers from developing countries being small farmers. In India, the agriculture labourers are unskilled and spread across 5.6 lakh villages. In light of their unorganized nature, agricultural workers do not have much bargaining power, which explains why they receive low wages. Money lenders and commission agents exploit them because they are more than their demand because they belong to the depressed classes, which have been neglected in Indian society for centuries.

Das Smitashree and Mapatra B.P. (3 May, 2022) they have studied working condition of women in Cuttack district of Odisha. A majority of women work for a daily wage, sowing, storing, and preparing land, and cooking, taking care of children, and washing clothes and utensils in the household. It is estimated that 52% of unorganized workers work in agriculture and related sectors, working between 2 and 8 hours a day. Women are quite unhappy with the low wages for their hard work. Furthermore, they are extremely vulnerable to poverty because of low and irregular wages, wage discrimination between men and women, a lack of public holidays, and a lack of standard working hours. There are also

issues relating to working conditions, dignity, seasonal unemployment, and harassment. Unpaid work, wage discrimination, low wages, dual responsibility, rigid tradition, lack of training facilities, triple burden of work are some of the challenges they face.

Dasgupta Sukti and M. Sudarshan Ratna (2011) in their study, a discussion was held about NREGA and how it impacts agricultural women in India in terms of participation, employment, wages, and poverty. In comparison to men, women seem to have fewer employment options, because they are more illiterate, unskilled, and less able to find work outside of agriculture. In the NREGA, women are given the opportunity to work in their villages, and this impacts their earnings since it is supposed to be at minimum wage. By bringing together many women with similar backgrounds in the workplace, NREGA provides an opportunity for women's voices and the organization to interact. Rajasthan and Tamil Nadu have higher rates of women participating in NREGA than Gujarat, Maharashtra, and Uttar Pradesh. Women contribute more than 70 percent to NREGA workdays in Rajasthan and Tamil Nadu. Since there are more women working in NREGA in states with a higher gender wage gap, NREGA wages are likely to increase the actual wages of women in agriculture in those states. There may be a reduction in the gender wage gap if men's wages do not increase proportionately.

Dev Mahendra S. (March, 1988) the aims of researcher is to analyze the

variation of state level poverty and ensure that full employment at the existing wage rate is insufficient to improve the standard of living of poor landless agriculture labour households. Secondary data have been gathered using different government reports. According to him, poverty is particularly prevalent among households whose primary source of income is wage work. As a result of raising wages, creating new jobs, improving productivity, and creating new assets, their living conditions can be improved. Poverty is larger than different employment schemes, as well as different employment schemes. It has been estimated that India's agriculture labour households have increased from 14.1 million (20%) in 1963 to 30.9 million (30.7%) in 1983. Poverty has increased from 52% in 1963-64 to 56% in 1977-78, but has declined by 42% in 1983-84. A higher incidence of poverty always occurs among agriculture labourers households in all states than among self-employed households.

What is Agricultural Labour?

1. 'According to the First Agriculture Labour Enquiries (1950-51) "All those who are engaged as hired labours in agricultural operation for 50 percent or more of the total number of days worked by them during the previous years."
2. "According to the Second Agricultural Labour Enquiry Committee (1956-57) "A person, if his or her major source of

income during the previous year was agricultural wages."

3. "According to the National Commission on Labour- "Who is basically unskilled and unorganized and has little for his livelihood other than personal level."
4. "According to the Committee on Labour Welfare (1969) "One whose principal means of livelihood is wage income arising out of farm labour and other allied activities."
5. According to the Census 2011: "A person who and other allied activities works in another person's land for wage in cash, kind or share in crops. Such a person had no risk in cultivation but merely worked in another person's land for wage with no right of lease or contract in the land and whose main source of income is wage employment for work on land or land based activities."

As defined by the First and Second Agricultural Labour Enquiry Committees, agricultural labourers work for hire and are paid in cash or kind. Agriculture labourers were defined as unskilled and unorganised workers who worked on land or other for their livelihood on a daily wage basis by the National Commission on Labour and Committee on Labour Welfare (1969).

Data Analysis:
Variation in the Agricultural Labourers in in Latur District (1991, 2001 and 2011.)

According to the censuses held in 1991, 2001, and 2011, the following table shows the total number of agricultural labourers in Latur district.

Table 1. Number of Agricultural Labourers in Latur District (1991, 2001, 2011)

Census Year	Number of Agricultural Labourers in Latur District.					
	Total	Total Variation	Male	Male Variation	Female	Female Variation
1991	2,58,428	-----	1,69,580	----	88,848	-----
2001	3,14,513	+56,085	1,52,073	-17,507	1,62,440	+73,592
2011	4,19,578	+1,05,065	2,24,374	+72,301	1,92,204	+29,764

Source: Latur District Gazetteer-2008, Latur District Census Hand Book 2001 and Latur District Census Hand Book 2011.

Variation in the Total Numbers of Agri. labourers:

The variation in the total number of agricultural labourers in Latur district from 1991 to 2001 and 2001 to 2011 is shown in the above table. In 1991, 2, 58,428 agricultural workers were employed, but by 2001, 3, 14,513 were employed. During this decade, the number of agricultural workers varied by 56085. Whereas. In 2011, the total 4, 19,578 agricultural labourers were employed thus the total agricultural labourers varied by 1, 05,065 during the decade 2001 to 2011.

Variation in the Total Male Agri. Labourers:

In 1991, the total 1, 69,580 males were employed, but 1, 52,073 males were employed in 2001. Thus, the number of male agricultural labourers has declined by -17,507 during the decade 1991 to 2001. The total number of 2, 24,374 male were working as agricultural labourers in 2011. If we compare this figure to the number of previous year the total variation is 72,301. Thus the total number of male agricultural labourers has

declined the decade 1991 to 2001 and it has increased in the decade 2001 to 2011.

Variation in the Total Female Agri. Labourers:

In 1991, the total 88,848 female agricultural labourers were employed, but 1, 62,440 were employed in 2001. Thus, the total numbers of 73,592 female agricultural labourers have increased in the decade 1991 to 2001. The total number of 1, 92,204 female agricultural labourers were employed in 2011. If we compare this figure with the total number of previous year, the total variation is 29,764. Thus it can be concluded that, the total number of female agricultural labourers has increased in the both decades.

The variation in the total number of agricultural labourers along with male and female has shown in the following graph.

Percentage of Variation in the Number of Agri. Labourers:

The percentage in the variation in the number of agricultural labourers has explained in the following table.

Decades	Percentage of variation in Agricultural Labourers in Latur District.		
	Percentage of Total Variation	Percentage of Male Variation	Percentage of Female Variation
1991-2001	3.34%	1.04%	4.39%
2001-2011	5.05%	3.48%	1.43%

Note: The percentage of variation is calculated from the total population of the previous years, 1991 and 2001.

The percentage of variation in the number of total agricultural labourers along with male and female has been calculated in the above table. It shows that, in the decade 1991-2001, the total agricultural labourers have increased by 3.34% and it has increased by 5.05% in the decade 2001-2011. The total number of male agricultural labourers has declined by 1.04% in the decade 1991-2001 and it has increased by 3.48% in the decade 2001-2011. The total number of female has increased by 4.39% in the

decade 1991-2001 and it has increased by 1.43% in the decade 2001-2011. It has shown in the following graph.

Conclusions:

1. The total number of agricultural labourers has increased in both decades but the increasing percentage in the decade 2001-2011 is more than the decade 1991-2001.
2. The variation in the male agricultural labourers is negative in the decade 1991-2001 because the number of male agricultural labourers has declined by 1.04%. But, in the decade 2001-2011 it has increased again by 3.48%.
3. The total number of female agricultural labourers has increased in the both decades but the increasing percentage in the decade 1991-2001 is more than the decade 2001-2011.

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